

The **Senior Scientist**

Name: Paulo
Age: 45
Gender: male
Affiliation: University

Statement: "I'm Paulo, a senior scientist working with soil data! I've heard a lot about FAIR data recently in conferences and meetings, and I want to make sure that any data I publish from now on is FAIR. "

Behaviour: He likes to work and learn in ways that are efficient as possible and enjoys quick tutorials and short and to the point explanations. He is very helpful and likes to support others.

The **PhD student**

Name: Jemal
Age: 30
Gender: male
Affiliation: Research Center

Statement: "Hey everyone! I am Jemal, a first year PhD student on a research visit in Germany. I really need to gather a lot of data for my PhD! Along the way I would also like to expand my knowledge on best practices within my field, find some useful tools that can help me with my studies and of course meet other scientists in my field and hopefully collaborate with them. "

Behaviour: He has many ideas and likes to try things out. He is open and positive.

The **PostDoc**

Name: Mary
Age: 34
Gender: female
Affiliation: Research Center

Statement: "I'm Mary, a researcher coming to the end of my first PostDoc position! I have been offered a position as a research associate in a slightly different topic, so I feel I need more practical training in order to do my new tasks correctly. "

Behaviour: She is reliable and positive about everything. Mary is undemanding and has no particular expectations. She is also enthusiastic and forgiving of mistakes.

The **Professor**

Name: Burkhard
Age: 64
Gender: male
Affiliation: University

Statement: "Hello! I am Burkhard a, soon to be retired, geology professor. I would really like to share all my data with other scientists but there is so much new to me. I would like to get assistance from someone who I can speak directly with, either by phone or email."

Behaviour: Burkhard is responsible, sets rules and likes to be in control. He likes to plan everything so that everything runs as smoothly as possible.

The **Master Student**

Name: Eya
Age: 22
Gender: diverse
Affiliation: University

Statement: "Hey, my name is Eya. I am a Master's student in Earth Sciences and I am starting my Master's thesis in Paleontology. I have already got data, but I am supposed to analyse more and I need support."

Behaviour: Eya is a person who likes to break out of the mainstream. Eya likes to use things differently from their intended purpose. This brings dangers, but also opens up new possibilities.

The **Data Steward**

Name: Valerie
Age: 42
Gender: female
Affiliation: Research Department

Statement: "My name is Valerie and I started working as a Data Steward 9 months ago. So far, there is no coordinated data management at the institute where I work. I have some knowledge in the field, but building an all-encompassing DM is a great challenge."

Behaviour: Valerie uses things intuitively. She browses through websites, clicks around a lot. She tends not to read long descriptions and explanations. She is not always absolutely purposeful.

The **Private Person**

Name: Nisrin
Age: 48
Gender: female

Statement: "I'm Nisrin and I had a bit of bad luck recently. My house was damaged after heavy rain caused flooding. Now I am on the phone almost daily with the insurance company, who need various documents from me and I need an expert providing a statement for my claim."

Behaviour: Nisrin likes when problems can be solved quickly and efficiently. She will follow guidance when it is provided by trustworthy sources.